

CRITERIAS FOR RETELLING LITERARY WORKS

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Abstract. This article discusses some methods of retelling literary works to help students master the certain work to the stage of performance requirements, the creation of the word through thought, and psychological processes.

Keywords. Speech technique, composition, expressive development, dramatization, character, methodology.

Introduction. The masters of stage speech S.Inomkhodjaev, L.Khodjaeva, in their scientific research have repeatedly emphasized the incomparable power of the art of words, especially the artistic word. The word that gives grace to human speech appears in fiction in a more impressive way, increases its aesthetic impact. That is why the art of expressive reading is highly valued in all periods and stages of social life. "The main reason why the art of expressive reading has a wide social status is its high spiritual and aesthetic power." [1. P. 4.]

In the theatre field, as in many fields, the power of the word is fragmentary. This is reflected in the careful acquisition of knowledge, memory, eloquence and speech skills. In order to acquire it, it is desirable to embody certain skills.

Speaking skills have two factors. One is to know the nature of speech, and the second is to master the technique of speech. If the clarity, logic, purity, richness, expressiveness, effectiveness, appropriateness of the speech are its characteristics, then the sound, diction, pause, accent, tone, intonation in the written speech are speech techniques. The student's thinking technique is strong but his voice is low; If it is ineffective or, on the contrary, if he/she does not have a clear voice and a sharp breath, everything is useless. It is desirable both being soft. [2.P.6.]

When absorbing the above ideas in students, it is desirable to understand the criteria of storytelling and retelling and to apply it in practice.

Body part. Retelling is a creative repetition of a literary text. It is very useful for students to retell the selected work to enrich their memory and imagination while working with students on descriptive literary pieces, one-story and full-story literary pieces in the science of stage speech. Through this process, the student's speech will be enriched with ideas. They begin to memorize and use metaphorical expressions, emotionally colored speech and expressions, and they understand and express the Uzbek language better.

The high artistry, compositional form and integrity of the language of the works proposed for retelling will teach the student to build a story clearly and coherently without getting carried away by details and without missing the main point will help him/her develop speaking skills. When choosing works for retelling, the teacher should take into account the following requirements for them, which are, high artistic value, ideological direction, dynamism, conciseness and at the same time figurativeness of presentation, clarity and sequence of speech and action, entertainment, as well as the presence of content and its size is considered. Retelling a small piece of work is easy for a student. It plays an important role in memorizing it and bringing it to the art level of artistic reading. Initially, the above instructions are suitable when working on folk tales and short stories.

Methodology. The methodology of teaching the retelling of a literary work in groups to the process of performance on stage has its own characteristics, but there are also general methodological methods. The lesson plans for retelling the work in all groups is seen in the primary reading of the work, discussion on questions, repeated reading, repetition.

In this process, the teacher asks questions about the extent to which the students understand the work. Before starting the retelling, it is necessary to remind the students the logic of the story, the interrelationship and interaction of the characters. In the process of retelling, the student's answer is supplemented or improved by the teacher.

Methodological literature recommends extensive use of the retelling plan.

If the student forgets the text or the words, it is used again. Instructions help students to understand or clarify the meaning of certain expressions, phrases, words and develop expressiveness¹ of speech during retelling.

Now going to process. In this phase, the teacher has two tasks: teaching students to perceive the text first read by the teacher, and then perceiving the story itself.

Divide the class into small groups and teach simple storytelling. For example, one of the Uzbek folk tales is the tale of the Golden Watermelon. [3. P.42.]

Once upon a time, there was a poor farmer. He had small piece of land. A farmer earned his living there by working day and night. Spring had come. The farmer began to plow the land. After plowing the land twice, he was cooling off on the bank of a large stream nearby, when a stork fell down while flying in the sky. When the farmer looked, the stork's wing was broken. The farmer immediately took the stork home and fed it for some time by tying a piece of wood to its broken wing. The stork got well and flew away.

One day, the farmer was sowing seeds when a stork flew by. The farmer continued sowing the seed. But the stork flew down again. During this crossing, three pieces of watermelon seeds were dropped by the stork.

After a few days, a watermelon seed sprouted along with the seed. Crops were planted on time, watered and plowed. So the time has come to harvest. One day he picked three watermelons and took them home. Watermelons were very big. The farmer invited his close relatives to his house. At one moment, when he wanted to cut a watermelon, the knife did not go in. He tried to cut the second one by putting it down, but the knife did not go through, and so did the third one. Everyone, the farmer and the guests were surprised. They hit the watermelon to the ground and looked at it, it was full of gold. The other two were also opened. They were also full of gold. The poor man was happy and shared everything with the guests, who were also happy and went their homes.

¹ Expressiveness - a set of semantic-stylistic signs of a language unit; ensures that the language unit can be a means of expression of the subjective (positive or negative) attitude of the speaker towards the content of the speech or the person to whom the speech is directed.

The teacher helps students to remember the sequence of appearance of a tale heroes, their actions. The beginning of the tale, as a rule, is well remembered, so the student retells it himself. In addition, the teacher joins the retelling process when the student has difficulties, the student then repeats one or two words or a whole sentence. Gradually, students move on to answering questions. The teacher's questions should be aimed at determining the sequence of events, naming the characters, recalling the lyrics of the songs. After small-volume folk tales, you can move on to retelling small stories with a simple plot. An example of such artistic works can be seen in the stories of A. Qakhor.

A variety of performances play an important role in preparing students for retelling. Dramatization of literary works with the help of puppets, shadows, table theater, flannel graph, etc. creates the necessary emotional mood, helps to develop interest in literary works, as well as better memorizing them, awakens in them the desire to convey their impressions.

To strengthen retelling skills, it is important to work individually in the morning and evening, especially with students who are not active enough in individual lessons. More complex tasks are solved when teaching retelling to students with lower mastery: they are taught to retell not only familiar, but also short stories and stories read for the first time in class. Special attention should be paid to the choice of repertoire. If the selected work matches the student's speech ability and character, it will be easy for the student to master this work. After reading a fairy tale or story, the teacher conducts a short conversation with the students about what they have read. His questions should be aimed at determining whether students understand the content of the work, the sequence of events, as well as some means of artistic expression. If it is difficult for the student to retell, the teacher asks him additional questions. Students in the class can also be involved in the process. They remind some phrases from the text, forgotten words. Gradually, the demands of retelling increase from lesson to lesson. The teacher achieves the accuracy and completeness of retelling in the student, the expressive transmission of the dialogue of the characters. If the student retells the text with his

own words, the teacher is sure that the author's idea is clearly repeated. Preparing students to retell the work can be done according to the following plan.

At the first lesson, the teacher lets the students read a literary piece of work or a single-event literary piece of their choice independently and expressively. Then he/she encourages the students to retell the memorized text. In this case, the students begin to narrate the texts they have read by mentally remembering the sequence of words.

An important methodological tool is the assessment of students retelling. When evaluating the retelling, it is necessary to briefly analyze it, highlight the good sides and shortcomings, encourage the student's efforts, give him/her confidence in his/her abilities. At the same time, another problem needs to be solved. Absorbing the ability of students to notice inconsistencies in the text when retelling each other. The teacher should create conditions that help the development of speech activity and independence of all students. If in the first semester of the first year you can call those who expressed a desire to retell the literary text, then in the future it is necessary to ensure that every student participates in retelling. When working with students, new tasks of teaching retelling of literary works are put forward. Being able to convey the content of a story or a tale in a consistent, expressive manner without the help of the teacher's questions; conveying dialogic speech, changing intonations according to the actors' experiences; use of expressive means.

Students are offered works with more complex plots in both semesters of the second year. In a large group, the stories of Uzbek folk tales, Cholpon, Gofur Ghulam, Oybek, Parda Tursun, Khakim Nazir, Abdulla Qahhor, Russian writers Leo Tolstoy, A.P. Chekhov and many other writers' works are retold. The methodology of lessons for teaching retelling depends on the level of development of coherent speech in this group of students, the tasks set by the teacher, as well as the characteristics of the proposed literary text. Students in the course are involved in evaluating the stories of their peers. Conducting such discussions is methodologically difficult, it requires great tact from students, knowledge of students' individuality. In this way, the mastering of the work chosen by the students will be faster and easier.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that it is very useful to follow some requirements in the development of speech by retelling the text.

First, read the text expressively, with emphasis and pauses.

Secondly, understanding the meaning of words and sentences in the text.

Thirdly, the main purpose of the text is to understand who and what it is aimed at.

It is appropriate to approach the text with questions such as why, what for, for what reason, for what purpose.

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